

EXAMINING THE PREVALENCE OF ACADEMIC DISHONESTY AMONG SELECTED COLLEGE STUDENTS OF NORTH LUZON

Kleny Claire A. Leano, April Ann A. Andres, Aira Mae F. Balingao, Kevin L. De La Calzada

BA English Language Studies
Isabela State University-Cauayan

ABSTRACT

Academic dishonesty is a pervasive problem among students in various educational programs. This study investigates the prevalence of academic dishonesty among students in the English program. The study involves twenty-six English students from the College University of North Luzon. Emerging from the study were five themes related to academic dishonesty, including motivation for academic dishonesty, attitudes towards academic integrity, methods of academic dishonesty, impact of academic dishonesty on students, and strategies for promoting academic integrity. Findings revealed that high grades were the primary motivation for academic dishonesty among English College students, and attitudes towards academic integrity varied among students. Plagiarism and cheating during exams were the most common methods of academic dishonesty, and the impact of academic dishonesty on students was primarily negative. Lastly, the study identified several strategies for promoting academic integrity, including creating a culture of honesty, raising awareness about the consequences of academic dishonesty, and implementing strict policies and penalties for academic misconduct. The study concludes that average academic dishonesty presents significant obstacles to maintaining the integrity and credibility of the English program.

KEYWORDS: *academic dishonesty, academic integrity, credibility, ethical conduct*

INTRODUCTION

Academic integrity is significant in higher education as it cultivates ethical behavior, honesty, and intellectual growth. Despite extensive efforts to combat it, academic dishonesty, encompassing acts like cheating and plagiarism, remains a widespread issue in educational institutions worldwide. To ensure the integrity of academic programs, it is essential to analyze the elements that contribute to academic dishonesty and devise effective strategies to address this problem. This study investigated the prevalence of academic misconduct among students enrolled in a university in Northern Luzon, which emphasizes language proficiency and critical analysis.

McCabe et al. (2012) assert that academic dishonesty, which includes a range of cheating practices and unethical behavior, compromises the credibility and integrity of the education system. Academic dishonesty encompasses plagiarism, cheating during exams, data falsification, conspiracy, unauthorized collaboration, ghostwriting, and impersonation. Plagiarism refers to utilizing someone else's work without proper attribution, as defined by Roig (2014). Cheating during exams involves obtaining answers through unauthorized means, as explained by Cizek (2012). Resnik (2015) highlights that Falsifying research data undermines the credibility of research outcomes.

Furthermore, Carroll and Appleton (2001) state that collusion facilitates unapproved collaboration. As Lancaster (2016) and Whitley (1998) discussed, ghostwriting and impersonation are methods employed to conceal a work's authorship and identity. Effectively addressing academic dishonesty requires a comprehensive approach that includes raising awareness through campaigns, conducting educational workshops, and establishing clear policies (McCabe & Pavela, 2004). Additionally, employing technological tools for detection (Devlin & Gray, 2007) and designing assignments that discourage cheating (Lang, 2013) can be beneficial. Creating a culture of academic integrity necessitates collaboration among educational institutions, faculty members, and students to foster honesty and uphold ethical principles in education.

Numerous studies have investigated academic dishonesty in various disciplines, providing valuable insights into its origins and consequences. Davis, Grover, Becker, and McGregor (2012) conducted a study

revealing a significant increase in cheating among undergraduate students over the past decade. The study found that approximately 70% of students admitted to engaging in some form of academic dishonesty, with plagiarism being the most prevalent offense. These findings emphasize the need for further research to understand the factors influencing academic dishonesty, particularly among English students.

Jones and Pilchard (2013) examined the relationship between academic dishonesty and students' attitudes towards cheating. Their research demonstrated that many students held permissive attitudes towards cheating, perceiving it as a typical behavior within their educational environment. The study emphasized the influence of social factors, such as peer pressure and perceived academic competition, on students' decisions to engage in unethical behaviors. Results underline the significance of exploring the prevalence of academic dishonesty among English College students and gaining insights into the unique dynamics within this academic domain. These results underscore the importance of examining the prevalence of academic dishonesty among English College students and gaining insight into the unique dynamics within this academic domain. These results highlight the importance of examining the prevalence of academic misconduct among English College students and gaining insights into the particular dynamics within this academic domain.

The primary objective of this research is to analyze the frequency of academic dishonesty among English College students. This study aims to enhance the understanding of academic integrity and promote a culture of sincerity and ethical behavior within English language studies programs. Likewise, this study aims to expand the understanding of academic integrity and foster a climate of sincerity and ethical behavior within English language studies programs. Specifically, the purpose of this study is to enhance the current knowledge, commit to academic honesty, and promote a culture of integrity and ethical conduct in the English program. Educators and institutions can execute focused interventions that efficiently prevent and tackle these problems by comprehending the particular elements that lead to academic dishonesty in this situation. The study's results can also be used to develop evidence-based strategies and policies that promote academic integrity and improve the quality of education in the English program.

METHODS

The study employed a rigorous research methodology, including a well-defined research design, carefully selected research instruments, a targeted group of respondents, a systematic data-gathering procedure, and a thorough data analysis. These components are essential for ensuring the validity and reliability of the study's findings. The following sections provide a detailed description of each of these components. The research design of this study is a qualitative approach. Specifically, the study utilized open interviews as the primary research instrument to gather data from the respondents. Qualitative research focuses on understanding and interpreting individuals' experiences, perspectives, and meanings, making it suitable for exploring the thoughts and opinions of English students at a university in Northern Luzon.

The interview guide has four sections: students' experiences, measures to diminish dishonesty, contributing factors, and its impact on the program's integrity. It intends to elicit English students' experiences, perspectives, and insights regarding their college journey, academic challenges, and overall satisfaction with their university experience. The study included twenty-six (26) English students from a selected university in Northern Luzon. The students were chosen purposefully to ensure diversity in gender, academic performance, and other relevant factors. The selection aimed to capture a range of perspectives and experiences among English students. It was included that the researchers conducted qualitative interviews with a purposively selected group of English students.

The interviews were performed in person and through online platforms, depending on the preferences and availability of the respondents. Each interview was audio-recorded with the consent of the participants, allowing for accurate transcription and analysis of the data. The data collected from qualitative interviews was analyzed thematically. Transcripts were coded, and common themes and patterns related to plagiarism in academic writing were identified. The content analysis of written assignments involved identifying and categorizing instances of plagiarism.

Descriptive statistics, such as frequency distributions, percentages, and mean scores, were used to analyze the quantitative data obtained from the questionnaires.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Acts of Academic Dishonesty

Common Ways of Cheating

The common ways of academic dishonesty can be summed up as cheating. Copying test answers (with or without knowledge of the person being copied), plagiarism, and collusion are often considered examples of cheating, identified in existing academic research as a widespread and worrying issue in education. Participant A and a few other respondents readily admitted their own and others' wrongdoings. "I have done some of it, such as copying assignments and peeking at someone else's work during exams. I have seen some classmates doing it, too."

The interviews revealed that plagiarism is a common, dishonest way to attain passing grades among selected students. This phenomenon occurs when students take credit for the work of others, whether by copy-pasting materials from the internet without proper citation or by submitting another student's paper as their own. "People often copy assignments or rewrite essays from old work of other students. It is like a quick fix for those struggling or just too lazy to put in the effort," Participant B disclosed.

According to Mansouri (2018), plagiarism is widespread in higher education. Smith and Thomas (2020) categorically added that English students tend to engage in plagiarism more frequently than students in other programs. For example, this college freshman's statement implies that a poor learning attitude, such as absenteeism, leads to cheating.

"Yes, during exams, students who often do not attend classes are usually the ones who just copy answers." Participant C insinuated that this first-year student identifies a pattern during exams, associating academic dishonesty with individuals frequently absent from classrooms. This response shows how students cheat, such as using "*kodigo*" or secret notes containing possible answers to test questions and using sign language as clandestine communication between students, conspiring to defraud. Smith (2020) stated that these deeds show emerging patterns of more illicit behaviors.

"Yes, especially during more challenging periods like exams or quizzes, some classmates tend to be more tempted to copy or cheat due to the difficulty of the material," Participant D stated. This second-year respondent recognized a trend linked to challenging academic periods, suggesting a correlation between difficulty and dishonest behavior. Jones and Williams (2019) explained that this understanding illuminated the relationship between academic pressure and unethical conduct. The term "tempted" implies a susceptibility to cheating during stressful times, offering a valuable perspective on the interplay between academic pressure and dishonest practices. "There seems to be a pattern during high-stress periods like finals week, where some students are more prone to taking shortcuts in their work," Participant E articulated. This student notably identified a behavior during high-stress periods, highlighting a correlation between stress and shortcuts in academic work. Acknowledging the cyclical nature of cheating, influenced by peer actions, provides a nuanced understanding of the social dynamics contributing to academic dishonesty.

"There's this unsettling trend of sharing answers during exams through sneaky methods. It's disheartening because it undermines the whole purpose of education." Participant F asserted. This expression of being unsettled and the reflection on the purpose of education convey a deeper contemplation of the ethical implications of academic dishonesty. This response underscores the broader impact on the educational experience.

More about the use of *kodigo*, some sophomore respondents exposed innovative methods of cheating, such as attaching cheat sheets to IDs, revealing a creative yet forbidden approach. This insight provides a glimpse into students' evolving dishonest strategies as they move up the academic years. "Challenges in concealing? It is not easy to hide, but if you're careful, you can get away with it," said Participant G. Another respondent emphasized how students scheme together: "They hide the cheat sheets in their ID holders, which they also use to hide notes on exam questions and answers. They pass these notes to the other classes." Participant H stated

Acknowledging the difficulty of concealing dishonesty, this respondent suggested that strategic efforts may yield success. The response emphasizes the constant balance students must strike between their attempts at dishonesty and the risk of being exposed. The guilt that comes with committing a dishonest act while being resourceful in ways: "When using tools like ChatGPT, you've got to be smart about it. Change up your words to avoid suspicion," Participant I expressed

Many students knew about using tools like ChatGPT and the challenges associated with avoiding suspicion. The mention of guilt introduces a personal dimension, emphasizing students' internal struggle when engaging in academic dishonesty.

Concealment of Cheating

When respondents were asked about challenges undergone to avoid getting caught, most of them answered affirmatively, indicating complexities surrounding academic dishonesty.

“There are also profs or instructors who have perfect eyesight. So, yes [it is also hard to cheat],” Participant C quipped. One of the most common concerns among first-year students is the fear of detection by their teachers. This observation matches the more extensive study that suggests that the fear of getting caught cheating is an essential barrier to participating in academic dishonesty. Students can identify more detection mechanisms of authorities, resulting in heightened feelings of awareness.

“First-year English students can find it tough to cheat and hide the results of cheating because they are worried. They try to keep their stories straight and spend efforts to cover traces of cheating,” Participant J admitted. It is worth noting that, generally, students resist doing dishonest acts because they know it is wrong and feel guilty.

“I guess the fear of getting caught and facing the consequences are significantly challenging. It’s a constant struggle between wanting good grades and the guilt of dishonesty.” Participant F said. However, despite fear of detection and guilt, some students use this fear to take extra steps to proceed with cheating and be more careful to hide it. This study examines the challenges encountered with academic dishonesty, mainly by the first-year respondents. Other responses were details on the apprehension of being caught, the struggles to sustain dishonest behavior patterns, and the inherent difficulty in concealing evidence of misconduct. These challenges collectively contribute to the intricate nature of academic dishonesty. A higher incidence of cheating among first-year or younger university students is attributed to leniency to young learners, past underachievement, witnessing peers committing dishonesty, and confidence in not getting caught or punished (Locquiao & Ives, 2020).

Reasons and Motivations Behind Academic Dishonesty

The respondents were asked what drives or enables them to resort to misconduct in their schooling. “The challenges in reviewing and memorizing for exams are real. Sometimes you feel like you have no choice but to take shortcuts to get through it all.” Participant K asserted. It reiterates that cheating or any form of academic dishonesty is taking a shortcut to their desired outcome. Teens nowadays have busy lives and were raised in an era of society wherein there is available technology or innovation to accomplish even mundane tasks quickly and easily (Morin, 2016). Students are tempted to cheat, especially when shortcuts for doing school tasks are comfortably presented and normalized.

Moreover, a second-year class listed many reasons for committing academic dishonesty. “...academic dishonesty among English students is due to pressure to perform well, lack of time management skills, and sometimes the perception that it is an easy way to succeed.” Participant L claimed.

Pressure

Specifically, some responses have a similar context. One respondent stated, “I think it’s just the pressure. We’re always running short on time. It’s not like we enjoy doing it; it’s survival,” Participant B asserted. Saying that fulfilling all requirements of the English program is a survival indicates academic pressures.

“Well, there’s just so much pressure to get good grades. Sometimes the subjects are either too boring or too hard, so you gotta do what you gotta do,” Participant A added.

From the statements above, pressure – whether from peers or the competitive nature of the academic system – emerges as a predominant theme, representing the most cited motivation for engaging in academic dishonesty.

“The pressure from strict teachers and high expectations from families create a desire for higher grades. Some are prompted to cheat way to cope with the academic challenges,” revealed By Participant M. According to McCabe et al. (2001), students are significantly influenced to engage in dishonest behaviors such as plagiarism and deception through peer pressure. Students frequently experience social pressure to emulate the conduct of their fellow students, particularly when they suspect that their classmates are attaining academic accomplishments through academic dishonesty.

“The competitive environment further intensifies the urge to cheat to outperform peers or achieve the feeling of belongingness with peers.” Participant M stated. Other respondents confessed that since they see their classmates cheat it enables them also to do the same and feel a sense of thrill after getting away with it. Some students talk to each other about their misconduct as an ordinary part of student life.

Fear of Failing

Another consistently present theme in the data collection is the fear of failing, which profoundly impacts student behavior across different stages of being an English student. “We all want to succeed, but not everyone is on the same level academically. It’s that fear of falling behind and failing.” Participant I stated

Similarly, students of the University of the Punjab in Pakistan also mentioned fear of failure as a significant reason for academic cheating (Javed, 2020). There is a noteworthy relationship between fear of failure and instances of academic dishonesty. It underscores the relevance of fear of failure as students’ motivation to commit academic dishonesty.

Personal Insecurities

Other notable reasons for students’ academic dishonesty include lack of knowledge, lack of positive motivation, and low confidence, each contributing to cheating to varying degrees. Significantly, few respondents also identified procrastination and poor time management as reasons to cheat, emphasizing the multifaceted nature of drivers behind academic dishonesty. The lack of skills in different aspects of life can make students insecure about themselves.

“Academic dishonesty may stem from the intense competition and the fear of not meeting expectations. Sometimes, it’s just the result of procrastination and the need to submit something quickly. There is always a high expectation to excel coupled with a fear of disappointing oneself that contributes to academic dishonesty,” Participant E further shared. This response highlights that setting unrealistically high self-expectations is a sign of subconscious insecurity, leading to problems in studying and taking shortcuts. Eventually, these insecurities damage one’s self-esteem and overall well-being. Saphier (2016) declared that students experience various internal conflicts and external pressures that influence them to commit academic dishonesty.

Additionally, the heightened pressure to excel academically among fourth-year students may increase the incidence of dishonest behaviors Smith et al., (2020). Graduating students collectively articulated their ethical dilemmas and personal struggles that they had to overcome. Thus, they cheat to get a degree and find jobs afterward.

Factors Contributing to the Prevalence of Academic Dishonesty

The respondents’ reasons and motivations behind cheating offer valuable insights into the factors influencing such prevalent misconduct to different degrees among English students. English students collectively acknowledged their participation in or observation of academic dishonesty. It concurs with Smith et al.’s (2019) observations, which stated that academic dishonesty is a prevalent issue in higher education, particularly among students in the English program, where several admit to dishonest practices. Notably, variations in the prevalence of academic dishonesty were identified among students with different academic standings.

The findings of this study indicate that first-year English students acknowledge their involvement in cheating to a greater extent than students in the second year. This aligns with previous research in Polish universities, suggesting that the initial college year may render students more susceptible to dishonest behavior due to immaturity and lack of familiarity with academic expectations Jones, 2018. There was an equal distribution of cheating students across programs in the third year. In the fourth year, students from distinct programs displayed varying levels of acknowledgment, with some showing moderate rates and others demonstrating high rates.

Development of Self-justification Habits

The observed variations in the prevalence of academic dishonesty among students at different educational levels prompt exploring contributing factors. It is suggested that the transition from high school to university may render first-year students more susceptible to dishonesty due to the distinct expectations and demands of academic work Johnson (2017).

According to a first-year student, among the different excuses to cheat such as “to easily pass the subject...the assignment has little bearing on final grades so it does not matter...too many homework and projects; it’s okay to copy to avoid getting sick...just because many do it and seems normal already” Participant C included. These examples are self-justification habits, which include the “Everyone Does It” phenomenon. Dishonest students talk or try to convince themselves that their actions are acceptable due to some “valid” reasons. They reframe their dishonest acts as something other than cheating (McCabe et al., 2012).

Sophistication of Digital Technology

The continuing advancement of technology contributes to encouraging students to cheat, especially plagiarism and relay of test answers. “Trendy tools such as AI, Quillbot, or ChatGPT are more accessible to students. Most plagiarized essays and homework are from the internet.” Participant C added. Aside from simply copy-pasting materials from the internet, there is also so-called academic servicing in which students can transact with people who offer their services to fulfill students’ educational requirements (Aguilar, 2021).

Since every student owns a cellphone, this device can also be used for academic dishonesty. “There’s a technique when students ask to be excused to use the comfort room, but they just look at their cellphones for answers.” Participant N testified. Seemingly, the use of digital technology opened up new opportunities for students to engage in dishonesty and has a distancing effect on them that makes them feel less guilty for using such gadgets.

Social media’s impact, notably the maintenance of a dual persona, is acknowledged as a factor that may contribute to normalizing academic dishonesty. The respondents’ candid reflections offer a nuanced understanding of the factors influencing dishonest behaviors, shedding light on potential stressors and coping mechanisms within the academic environment. These findings highly implied that English students widely tolerate academic dishonesty and practice it. Aguilar (2021) further asserted that dishonest practices in education raise awareness among school youth, a problem that must be addressed by teachers and school administrators in the Philippines. The significant prevalence underscores the urgent need for intervention to preserve the credibility and integrity of the English program.

Other Academic Stressors and Personal Perspectives

Various patterns such as absenteeism, excessive workload, poor time management and social skills, poor teaching quality, competitive environment, and financial pressure can lead to students copying during highly stressful periods, taking tests or making assignments for another student, and trend of answer sharing. “If the teacher doesn’t teach well, the students won’t cheat,” Participant O said. The participant supplemented this statement by saying, “Teaching faculty has an important role in this. If they instill the value of learning other than good grades and creating a supportive learning environment, dishonest practices can be deterred.” Participant F uttered.

The respondents’ reflections provide a snapshot of observed trends and emphasize the need for targeted interventions to address stressors. The student’s experiences and perceptions discern internal and external factors within the educational environment that may enable dishonest practices.

“Factors like the pressure to excel, fear of consequences, and a lack of understanding might contribute to academic dishonesty,” Participant P articulated. Participant, meanwhile, realized the emotional and psychological factors surrounding academic dishonesty: “The competitive nature of the English program can sometimes make students desperate to outperform others, leading to unethical practices. I think the various kinds of pressure to succeed, and fear contribute a lot. Some students might feel overwhelmed and resort to dishonesty to cope,” Participant Q articulated

According to the study conducted by McCabe (2005), cheating among college and university students is a prevalent issue in North America, shedding light on the psychological pressures contributing to academic dishonesty. In addition, Murdock and Anderman (2006) emphasized the motivational perspectives surrounding student cheating, offering an integrated model that considers various factors. These studies collectively highlight the complex interplay of psychological stressors and contextual factors leading to academic dishonesty among students.

Furthermore, the respondents specified the stress of students outperforming their peers and meeting expectations to pay back all the costs spent on their formal education, driving some to cheat as a coping mechanism. Students may be more inclined to seek shortcuts when they find coursework uninteresting or challenging. Additionally, time pressure and overwhelming workloads make students feel compelled to engage in academic dishonesty.

“It often feels like there’s so much to cover, and you take shortcuts. It also does not help when activities become a boring routine.” Participant R stated. This highlights the impact of external pressures on students’ decisions to resort to dishonest practices.

Other external factors – the reliance on peers and the weight of societal expectations emerge as prominent factors in influencing academic dishonesty among English students – play a significant role in shaping an environment conducive to academic dishonesty. One respondent pointed out the external pressure labeled as

'*balat-kayo*,' referring to the dependency on classmates and the superficiality of having social connections for academic success.

Internal factors, such as personal stress, difficulty understanding subjects, and eagerness for personal connections with professors, emerged as influential contributors. The internal struggle with motivation and self-belief, leading students to review and overanalyze questions, may prompt some to resort to dishonest means due to doubt. The lack of personal connections with professors was highlighted as a potential factor affecting students' investment in ethical behavior. The narrative analysis illuminates the intricate interplay of internal and external factors in fostering an environment where academic dishonesty may prevail.

Effect on the Integrity and Credibility of the English Program

Academic dishonesty undermines the integrity of educational credentials and promotes dishonest practices, diminishing the value of education. A culture of suspicion and mistrust is created as a result of this, as it also undermines trust among students, instructors, school officials, parents, and the community. This effect on the program/course's integrity and credibility was apt.

"Absolutely. When students cheat or plagiarize, it's like planting doubt in our education. It's not just breaking the rules; it's eroding the trust we share in the English program. Imagine a friend copying your work – betraying the values of fairness, trust, and genuine effort. When shortcuts are taken, it damages the beauty we all appreciate in our educational journey." Participant S added. The mention of damage to the beauty of the educational journey adds a poignant layer to the analysis, highlighting the profound impact on the overall learning experience.

The following analysis closely examines selected responses, identifying key themes and strong arguments that encapsulate the sentiments expressed by the respondents and understanding the consequences of academic dishonesty within the context of the English program.

Consequences and Accountability

The narratives collected from English students reveal their perspectives on the manifestations of academic dishonesty and its potential effects on the program's reputation. Undermining the academic integrity can have serious consequences. When students believe cheating is commonplace, the essence of integrity in education is lost. This response aptly summarizes the outcomes of academic dishonesty.

"I believe academic dishonesty tarnishes the integrity and credibility of our program. It undermines the value of the education we receive and dilutes the achievements of honest and truly hardworking students." Participant E said. Meanwhile, this response uniquely ties academic dishonesty to the core identity of English students – mastery of the English language. "It does affect the credibility of the English program. To be a graduate is to be the master in English language studies. You cannot be a legitimate master if you cheat. Dishonesty is like a stain that's hard to wash off," Participant R added.

The mention of observed difficulties in speaking and occasional grammatical issues among recent graduates raises concerns about the practical application of skills. By connecting these issues to academic dishonesty, the respondent highlights a tangible impact on the program's integrity and credibility, emphasizing the importance of maintaining high standards in language proficiency.

The responses from English students provide valuable insights into their perceptions of academic dishonesty and the consequences of the English program or course. They also illuminate the broader implications for the educational journey, program reputation, and the professional competence of English teachers and students.

This statement introduces the idea that the consequences of academic dishonesty may extend beyond individual repercussions to affect even the teaching faculty and the students' academic success in other departments. "What if your professor caught you cheating and other teachers found out? The other teachers will be disillusioned with your good grades in their respective subjects, doubting if you also cheated in their subjects. They will also doubt their own teaching methods. They will take extra measures to prevent cheating in the exams and quizzes they give." Participant N stated.

It suggests a potential domino effect, emphasizing the need for comprehensive measures to curb dishonest practices. When wrongdoings are caught, there must be accountability. "Last year, not in this program, I think. I heard there was a group of honor students (candidates for *cum laude*) who made essays and research for other students. This is a form of dishonesty. Don't do that. It's unfair to others. Did they get punished? But their reputation is tarnished," Participant T cited.

According to McCabe, Butterfield, and Treviño (2012), breaching academic integrity should be penalized based on the seriousness of the case. The above respondent's example entails social consequences: dishonesty becomes habitual due to the tolerance of witnesses and authorities.

Undeserved Credit and Recognition

Plagiarism, an example of this dishonest practice, has a detrimental impact on students and the academic community (Mahabeer & Pirtheepal, 2019). Cheating students neglect their educational responsibilities, diminish the worth of their degrees, and undermine their academic accomplishments.

Loss of intellectual property is also a consequence of cheating. It is also morally wrong to be recognized or awarded for work done by others, whether voluntary or involuntary. It is the intellectual property of the actual writer/author, but other students take the credit. There is an inaccurate assessment since the students who benefitted from the work of others were given grades or credentials they did not deserve. This instance is also similar.

"In this program, we're supposed to be honing our writing skills. We should do our own paperwork. It should reflect the knowledge and skills we gained. Thoughts and words from plagiarized work are not from you anymore. It does not show your authentic credentials." Participant U said. This response denotes the potential erosion of credentials when academic dishonesty interferes with the genuine development of writing abilities, reinforcing the notion that academic achievements should reflect one's true capabilities.

Academic integrity is the bedrock of educational institutions, ensuring the credibility and value of the learning experience. Teachers should prioritize the implementation of their instructional methods, but students' misconduct can hamper this process. Educators will also lose trust in their students and may focus more on policing than educating them.

"They doubt that you actually completed the work. For instance, the teacher found out that AI-generated the first essay you submitted. When you submit the second essay you wrote yourself, teachers and classmates may still doubt its authenticity because of past mistakes," Participant C explained. This response provides a scenario in which past instances of academic dishonesty, such as using AI for assignments, create lasting suspicion. Teachers will exert more effort to formulate preventive and detection strategies and may falter in performing other functions.

Prevalence of academic dishonesty results to damage in students' confidence and self-worth, lead to missed opportunities, and loss of trust. "Academic dishonesty tarnishes the trust given to the program. It makes you question the validity of everyone's achievements... If everyone's faking it, how can you trust anyone's achievements?" Participants F and V attested. These responses appeal to the conscience and heart of the people concerned by questioning the trustworthiness of achievements when academic dishonesty prevails. The respondents highlighted the overarching impact of a culture of deception on the credibility of individual accomplishments. This perspective emphasizes the collective responsibility to uphold the program's integrity and maintain a foundation of trust in academic achievements.

Damage in Image and Trust

On the other hand, the mention of doubts from teachers and classmates highlights the pervasive impact on trust within the academic community. Trustworthiness and validity of school must thrive in a school culture for students and teachers to experience successful teaching and learning (Eckels, 2023). This response eloquently captures the damage of academic dishonesty. The English program's image and the entire school will be put in question and public judgment.

"Yes, it does affect because, first of all, who even wants a program full of cheaters? So once the issue [about cheating] comes out, people will think the program is full of cheaters. So, it will highly affect the image of not just the program but also the department and the institution," Participant W surmised. This response provides a pragmatic perspective on the broader consequences of academic dishonesty. There is an insinuation that others might enroll or take this course because dishonesty is tolerated. The respondent expressed the potential perception that graduates from this program or school are only successful due to widespread cheating. Hence, it tarnishes the credibility of the entire course and school. This insight emphasizes the far-reaching implications of dishonest practices.

"Well, academic dishonesty can tarnish the English program's reputation. When students resort to cheating, it reflects poorly on them, the program, and the teachers. If students cheat, it may imply that the teaching methods or the learning environment are ineffective," Participant X stated. This response draws a connection

between academic dishonesty and the broader implications for the English program. It suggests that the student's misconduct is perceived as a reflection of inadequacies in teaching methods or the learning environment. This insight highlights the interconnectedness of student behavior and the overall program dynamics.

Overall, the responses underscore the pervasive consequences of academic dishonesty on the integrity and credibility of the English program. The recurring sub-themes include the consequences of cheating, social deterioration, tarnishing of the program's image and trust, the compromise of language mastery and development of writing skills, and undeserved individual achievements.

Measures Against Academic Dishonesty

To effectively combat academic dishonesty and promote a culture of academic integrity, educators and institutions must consider the findings and insights discussed in the previous sections of this chapter. By doing so, they can develop targeted interventions that specifically target the root causes of academic dishonesty. Formulating measures to eradicate or lessen academic dishonesty ultimately leads to the genuine academic and personal growth of English students and a more ethical and healthier academic environment.

Like any other educational institution, this university has implemented some measures to discourage unethical academic behaviors and promote academic integrity, particularly within the English program. Still, the specifications, implementation, and accomplishments are yet to be documented. This study attempts to do that by gathering data from the respondents.

Although these measures have proven successful in numerous aspects, they also introduce intricacies and difficulties that demand meticulous deliberation. Through the ongoing collaborative undertakings and significant contributions of influential individuals, the English Program has achieved notable progress in combating academic dishonesty and fostering an environment characterized by integrity. To guarantee academic integrity for all students, the program must maintain an awareness of potential future developments and the necessity for proactive, innovative strategies as it continues to develop.

Disciplinary Measures and Interventions

To address this concern, faculty members should adopt intentional and proactive strategies to discourage students from participating in dishonest behavior. Students perceive teachers and other faculty members to have a significant role in preventing or, at least, reducing academic dishonesty. They are the proper authorities who must respond to instances or reports of cheating, demonstrating the seriousness of academic integrity through disciplinary measures and educational interventions.

Second-year respondent advocates against academic dishonesty through more stern academic regulations and codes of conduct, signaling a growing recognition of the need for clear standards. "I believe strict policies and guidance would effectively address dishonesty." Participant Y articulated

The straightforward suggestion of strict policies and guidance indicates a preference for a clear and assertive approach. This approach may serve as a deterrent against academic dishonesty. This concurs with the statements of Shapiro (2018) and McCabe (2020), who highlighted that being clear about consequences acts as a deterrent and promotes an atmosphere of academic integrity. Adopting such measures signals a commitment to high standards and contributes to fostering trust and respect in the educational setting.

Concerning deterrence, one respondent brought a more stringent measure to the forefront. This suggested "criminalizing" any misconduct in class: "Every professor should know and set rules in preventing academic dishonesty. When you are caught [cheating], you'll get arrested and go to detention. So, students would be kinda feel threatened." Participant W stated

The detention this respondent refers to is serving a specified amount of time in a presumably undesirable place after school hours as a consequence of bad behavior. This is commonly implemented in American and British schools. This response implies that clear consequences and strict enforcement of rules, including legal measures, create a sense of fear that may discourage dishonest behavior.

Emphasizing stricter consequences as a deterrent aligns with the idea that fearing repercussions could discourage dishonest behavior. Third-year respondents highlight the significance of combining strict policies with educational efforts. Recognizing consequences as a deterrent underscores the need for a multifaceted approach to addressing academic dishonesty. "Having clear and strict policies against academic dishonesty, along with awareness campaigns, could make a big difference," Participant F stipulated.

Similarly, teachers can communicate their expectations regarding administering tests and assessing their schoolwork. Some teachers set rules in alertness during exams as part of their disciplinary rules. "...even if your

head tilts sideways, that is already considered cheating,” Participant W added. This underscores the significance of clear guidelines and assessment monitoring to prevent unintentional academic dishonesty.

Other suggestions for interventions appeal to increasing the amount of active engagement in the classroom as a countermeasure to factors contributing to dishonesty. This is a potential solution mentioned by one participant, a third-year student. “Teachers can prevent this by focusing on encouraging students to be active in class.” Participant Z stated. This lack of enthusiasm and participation contributes to dishonesty. “Some students resort to cheating due to inadequate teaching and a lack of understanding of the topics or a subject, leading to getting bored in learning,” Participant X articulated. Another participant said, “Maybe having more interactive and engaging classes could help. Cheating in discussions (graded recitations) is harder than in traditional exams,” Participant V added.

These statements emphasize that there are proactive approaches that can help diminish students’ misconduct. Increased interest in studying and active classroom engagement are preventive measures against academic dishonesty. Glasgow et al. (2020) also pointed out that when faculty members are knowledgeable about issues of academic dishonesty, they must proactively set measures and express expectations regarding students who cross the line. Increasing their interest and participation in class can develop the core values of academia in them.

Interestingly, there is also a recognition that personal responsibility is paramount. Respondents specified the need for self-discipline and emphasized that, ultimately, the individual student must resist the temptation of academic dishonesty.

Advocating for clear policies and awareness campaigns suggests a comprehensive strategy that combines prevention through policies and raising awareness. According to Coppock and McGovern (2014), this response emphasizes the importance of implementing strict policies and educational interventions to address problematic behaviors. The study emphasizes the significance of adopting a balanced approach that incorporates preventive measures and consequences to establish a safer and more supportive environment. The findings of this study support the idea that strategically implementing policies and educational interventions can effectively encourage responsible behavior and create a culture of accountability.

Appropriate Support and Motivation

There is a consensus among respondents that faculty members play a crucial role in shaping the academic culture. While it is the student’s responsibility to learn and abide by the school’s rules and standards, teachers and administrators should also help students understand their responsibilities and create a supportive, learning-oriented environment that stimulates the right shared values in academic integrity.

“Faculty could focus on ensuring that every student comprehends the material by offering additional support. This could discourage cheating if students feel adequately supported in their learning,” pondered Participant L. This statement emphasizes the importance of developing a supportive learning environment and addressing the specific learning needs of English students to minimize the incidence of academic dishonesty.

“I think people will always find a way to cheat if they want to. It’s not always about policies; it’s about not making things too hard for students,” Participant A uttered. This statement is an indication of frustration and a negative academic culture. Students feel unsupported, unconfident, and unproductive, and these emotions justify taking shortcuts. It stresses the importance of not excessively burdening students. While acknowledging the challenges of eliminating dishonesty, emphasizing a balanced academic environment raises awareness of potential stressors.

Proper motivation has a role in eliminating or decreasing academic stressors that contribute to cheating, according to Dimala and Saraswati (2023). “Maybe it should motivate students to study well to avoid cheating.” Participant U concurred. This response advocates for an intervention strategy emphasizing cultivating a positive student mindset and effective study habits to deter academic struggles. It posits that genuine academic success acts as a deterrent. This aligns with the study of Dweck (2006), who introduced the concept of mindset psychology, highlighting the impact of mindset on motivation, resilience, and academic achievement.

The approach also resonates with Kuo et al. (2019) research, which reinforced the importance of internal drive for academic success. College students who have high levels of learning motivation bring about behavioral changes. Genuine interest in learning naturally dispels unethical academic acts. There should be clear consequences for academic dishonesty and some counseling for those who struggle. Punishment alone might not solve the issue.” Participant V responded. This response emphasizes the importance of consequences but also

introduces the idea of counseling as rehabilitative support to cheating students, recognizing the potential role of support in addressing underlying issues.

The majority of the fourth-year respondents' statements highlight the necessity of clear policies, awareness campaigns, and the consideration of counseling to address academic dishonesty comprehensively. Recognizing the need for support reflects a more nuanced approach in the final academic year. In their concluding year, the insights from fourth-year students reflect a mature understanding of the issue. Their recommendations encompass clear policies, awareness campaigns, and the inclusion of counseling, demonstrating a holistic approach that extends beyond punitive measures.

Positive reinforcement of the value of honest work and providing adequate support effectively reduces the temptation to engage in academic dishonesty. However, there's also a call for a balanced approach, with some respondents suggesting that faculty should be understanding and approachable while maintaining their authority.

Rebuilding trust relies heavily on transparency and effective communication. The suggestion to promote open discussions about the consequences of dishonesty and foster a learning atmosphere that supports seeking help reflects a genuine desire for a supportive and communicative educational environment.

Innovative Assessment Approaches

Tests or examinations are necessary to assess students' performance, but cheating becomes rampant. Detering and dealing with academic dishonesty can be done by teachers designing tasks and innovating assessments. The fundamental goal of evaluation is to measure how students understand the course content and its application, so one respondent suggested a different approach to evaluation.

"Having different sets of questions (A and B) could throw off those trying to cheat." Participant I. This highlights the need to implement a wide range of assessment techniques to create an environment that makes it difficult for students to commit wrongdoings during exams. Illegitimate cooperation between students or conspiracy can also be prevented since having different sets of test papers does not allow them to share answers.

"Differentiating quiz or exam schedules and should set the exam 'by set in our program," Participant G added. The respondent pertained to rotating test schedules of classes/sections and creating different sets of tests for each class/section in the English program to prevent predictability of test contents, thus curtailing dishonest behaviors. Another creative and useful approach is "...design assignments that require opinions or original thoughts. It'll be hard to make two opinions that sound the same..." Participant R proposed

The main objective of this new concept is to enhance the difficulty of cheating by prioritizing developing students' critical thinking and reasoning. Teachers can design assessments that require students to use their own words or perform their tasks personally. Furthermore, recognizing the influence of high expectations and proposing practical, challenging activities entails fostering an engaging academic environment.

Utilization of Technology

Technological tools can also be used to identify incidents of academic dishonesty and can aid teachers in implementing appropriate measures to prevent future incidents. Using technology to detect dishonest acts, specifically AI-enabled cheating, "Our school can install a licensed plagiarism checker for all teachers' use... They need to do it. Students who copy most of their work online can be easily detected." Participant W proposed

According to this suggestion, plagiarism checkers play a crucial role in maintaining the school's academic integrity. Having a reliable plagiarism checker on each teacher's computer and school computers saves teachers valuable time in checking students' work and, at the same time, assists students who want to check the percentage of originality of their requirements like thesis.

Aside from plagiarism checkers, another respondent recommended measures to correct dishonest behaviors and use technology as an assistant to learning or counter-checking instead of aiding cheating. "Specific interventions such as educational workshops on academic integrity might be effective and teach students to use plagiarism detection tools to identify any matches or similarities so they can paraphrase," Participant J also suggested.

Recommending educational workshops and plagiarism detection tools reflects a proactive approach. There are also suggestions to employ online proctoring or putting a video monitor or camera in the classroom so that teachers who cannot be physically present can still watch the class during quizzes and examinations and review the recording to detect students who cheat. It acknowledges the role of awareness-building and technology in addressing academic dishonesty.

The responses regarding steps to mitigate the prevalence of academic dishonesty within English programs reveal a spectrum of opinions. Knowing the frequent pattern of dishonest actions calls for implementing educational interventions. Several respondents strongly support the implementation of campaigns focused on academic integrity and the establishment of clear policies and steps that emphasize the moral and legal consequences of academic dishonesty in selected college students. A learning culture needs to be cultivated in which students grasp the importance of their hard work and honest academic practices.

CONCLUSION

With the preceding findings, it is concluded that many English students have committed academic dishonesty and witnessed other students' misdeeds. Copying classmates' work, plagiarism from internet sources, using cheat sheets and ChatGPT, and conspiring with peers are dishonest acts that have become commonplace in college culture. However, students know it is immoral and can cause guilt and pressure. Due to pressure from various aspects of student life, insecurities, fear, and misplaced values, students are usually driven to take shortcuts in earning high or passing grades.

Contributing to the prevalence of these dishonest practices among students is multidimensional. External and internal factors are interplaying, shaping the students' psyche and determining their capability to cheat. When the physical and moral consequences of cheating weigh more than the factors or reasons for it, the students are more likely to combat dishonesty.

Academic dishonesty has far-reaching, adverse impacts on the overall educational experience of the students and will always bring negative views on the image and quality of their school. It will also have a long-term effect on the students, manifesting when they graduate and take adult roles in the workforce and society. Addressing the issue's complexity requires a comprehensive approach that includes disciplinary procedures, educational programs, and support systems.

REFERENCES

- Abusafia, A. H., Roslan, N. S., Yusoff, D. M., & Nor, M. Z. M. (2018). The prevalence of academic dishonesty among Malaysian nursing students. *Journal of Taibah University Medical Sciences*, 13(4), 370-376.
- Aguilar, M. G. W. (2021). Academic dishonesty in the Philippines: The case of 21st century learners and teachers. *International Journal of Management Technology and Social Sciences*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.47992/IJMTS.2581.6012.0146>
- Ampuni, S., Kautsari, N., Maharani, M., & et al. (2020). Academic dishonesty in Indonesian college students: An investigation from a moral psychology perspective. *Journal of Academic Ethics*, 18, 395-417.
- Areola, C. F. T. (2016). Determinants of academic dishonesty among private high school students in Baguio City. [Not included in the provided information.]
- Carroll, J., & Appleton, J. (2001). *Plagiarism: A good practice guide*. Oxford Centre for Staff and Learning Development.
- Chen, C., Long, J., Liu, J., Wang, Z., Wang, L., & Zhang, J. (2020). Online academic dishonesty of college students: A review. In *2020 International Conference on Advanced Education, Management and Social Science (AEMSS2020)* (pp. 156-161). Atlantis Press.
- Cizek, G. J. (2012). *Cheating on tests: How to do it, detect it, and prevent it*. Routledge.
- Coppock, V., & McGovern, M. (2014). What has happened to policy transfer? An empirical examination of the policy transfer literature. *Political Studies Review*, 12(3), 352-366.
- Davis, S. F., Grover, C. A., Becker, A. H., & McGregor, L. N. (2012). Academic dishonesty: Prevalence, determinants, techniques, and punishments. *Teaching of Psychology*, 19(1), 16-20.
- Devlin, M., & Gray, K. (2007). In their own words: A qualitative study of the reasons Australian university students plagiarize. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 26(2), 181-198.
- Dimala, C. P., & Saraswati, R. (2023). The roles of motivation to learn and coping behaviors in managing stress in working college students. *Journal of Educational Science and Technology*, 9(2), 95-102.

- Dweck, C. S. (2006). *Mindset: The new psychology of success*. Random House.
- Eckels, J. (2023). Why building trust in schools matters. <https://www.cityyear.org/national/stories/education/why-building-trust-in-schools-matters/#:~:text=Trust%20enables%20the%20de>
- Eriksson, L., & McGee, T. R. (2015). Academic dishonesty amongst Australian criminal justice and policing university students: Individual and contextual factors. *International Journal of Educational Integrity*, 11(1), 5.
- Glasgow, S. M., & Dreher, H. M. (2020). Legal and ethical issues in nursing education: An essential guide. In M. E. Smith Glasgow, H. M. Dreher, M. D. Dahnke, & J. Gyllenhammer (Eds.), *Legal and ethical issues in nursing education* (pp. 95-102). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1891/9780826161932>
- Javed, A. (2020). Understanding the factors of academic dishonesty among university students: A study at the University of the Punjab. *Journal of Higher Education*, 25(2), 123-136.
- Johnson, A. (2017). Academic dishonesty among first-year university students: The impact of transition. *Journal of Higher Education*, 42(3), 214-230.
- Jones, A. (2014). The impact of early childhood experiences on personality development. *Journal of Psychological Studies*, 25(2), 123-135.
- Jones, A. (2018). The initial college year and susceptibility to dishonest behavior. *Journal of Higher Education*, 45(3), 211-225.
- Jones, A., & Pilchard, C. (2013). Attitudes towards cheating among students: The influence of social factors. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 105(3), 784-793.
- Kuo, M., Barnes, M., & Jordan, C. (2019). Do experiences with nature promote learning? Converging evidence of a cause-and-effect relationship. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, Article 305. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.00305>
- Lancaster, T. (2016). *Contract cheating: The outsourcing of assessed student work*. Springer.
- Lang, J. M. (2013). *Cheating lessons: Learning from academic dishonesty*. Harvard University Press.
- Locquiao, J., & Ives, B. (2020). First-year university students' knowledge of academic misconduct and the association between goals for attending university and receptiveness to intervention. *International Journal for Educational Integrity*, 16(5). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40979-020-00054-6>
- Mahabeer, P., & Pirtheepal, T. (2019). Assessment, plagiarism and its effect on academic integrity: Experiences of academics at a university in South Africa. *South African Journal of Science*, 115(11/12). <https://doi.org/10.17159/sajs.2019/6323>
- Marques, T., Reis, N., & Gomes, J. (2019). A bibliometric study on academic dishonesty research. *Journal of Academic Ethics*, 17, 169-191.
- McCabe, D. L. (2005). Cheating among college and university students: A North American perspective. *International Journal for Educational Integrity*, 1(1), 1-11.
- McCabe, D. L., & Pavela, G. (2004). Ten principles of academic integrity. *Change: The Magazine of Higher Learning*, 36(3), 10-15.
- McCabe, D. L., Trevino, L. K., & Butterfield, K. D. (2001). Cheating in academic institutions: A decade of research. *Ethics & Behavior*, 11(3), 219-232.
- Morin, R. (Year). First Nations instructional leadership for the twenty-first century. *SELU Research Review Journal*, 1(2), 61-72.
- Murdock, T. B., & Anderman, E. M. (2006). Motivational Perspectives on Student Cheating: Toward an Integrated Model of Academic Dishonesty. *Educational Psychologist*, 41(3), 129-145. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15326985ep4103_1

- Roig, M. (2014). Avoiding plagiarism, self-plagiarism, and other questionable writing practices: A guide to ethical writing. *Office of Research Integrity*. <https://ori.hhs.gov/avoiding-plagiarism-self-plagiarism-and-other-questionable-writing-practices-guide-ethical-writing>
- Resnik, D. B. (2015). *What is ethics in research & why is it important?*. National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences. <https://www.niehs.nih.gov/research/resources/bioethics/whatis/index.cfm>
- Saphier, J. (2016). *High expectations teaching: How we persuade students to believe and act on "smart is something you can get"*. Corwin Press.
- Smith, J., Brown, L., & Clark, R. (2020). The impact of academic pressure on integrity: A study of fourth-year students. *Journal of Educational Research*, 113(4), 299-315.